

ON OMEGA LIMITING SET OF THE ISING MAPPING OVER \mathbb{Q}_2

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Abstract. Nowadays in the world, it is important to define the set of all periodic Gibbs measures for lattice systems with a finite or countable set of spin values. We notice that the studying such kind problems leads us to consider discrete dynamical systems over vector spaces. In this study, we examine the discrete-time dynamics of the Ising model over the field of p -adic numbers. It is well-established that the Ising model is relevant to the theory of Gibbs measures, and every periodic point of the mapping can be characterized as a Gibbs measure for the Ising type models. We demonstrate that the dynamics of the 2-adic Ising model are regular.

Keywords: p -adic numbers, discrete-time dynamical system, positive trajectory, omega limiting set.

Kalit so‘zlar: p -adik sonlar, diskret vaqtli dinamik sistema, musbat trayektoriya, omega limit to‘plam.

Ключевые слова: p -адические числа, дискретная динамическая система, положительная траектория, омега-предельное множество.

At present, p -adic analysis is a rapidly developing trend in mathematics [1]. Numerous applications of p -adic numbers have resulted in the theory of p -adic differential equations, p -adic probability theory, p -adic mathematical physics and so on. It is known that p -adic numbers are also closely connected with Diophantine equations, that is, with finding all the solutions of a system of polynomial equations or giving a bound for the number of the solutions over the field of p -adic numbers. We observe that, in general, the same Diophantine problem may have different solutions in the field of p -adic numbers and the field of real numbers because of the different topological structures.

Let \mathbb{Q} be the field of rational numbers. For a fixed prime number p , every rational number $x \neq 0$ can be represented in the form $x = p^r \frac{n}{m}$, where $r, n \in \mathbb{Z}$, m is a positive integer, and $(p, n) = (p, m) = (m, n) = 1$. The p -adic norm of rational number x is given by

$$|x|_p = \begin{cases} p^{-r}, & \text{for } x \neq 0, \\ 0, & \text{for } x = 0. \end{cases}$$

We note that such a norm satisfies the strong triangle inequality

$$|x + y|_p \leq \max\{|x|_p, |y|_p\}.$$

So, this norm is a non-Archimedean absolute value. Since strong triangle inequality, one has the following properties of the p -adic norm

- 1) if $|x|_p \neq |y|_p$ then $|x + y|_p = \max\{|x|_p, |y|_p\}$;
- 2) if $|x|_p = |y|_p$ then $|x + y|_p < |x|_p$.

One can check that \mathbb{Q} is not complete w.r.t. the p -adic norm. The completion of \mathbb{Q} with respect to $|\cdot|_p$ is denoted by \mathbb{Q}_p , and it is called the field of p -adic numbers.

Any $x \in \mathbb{Q}_p^\times$ can be uniquely represented in the canonical form

$$x = p^{\gamma(x)}(x_0 + x_1p + x_2p^2 + \dots),$$

where $\gamma(x) \in \mathbb{Z}$ and the integers x_j satisfy: $x_0 > 0$, $0 \leq x_j \leq p - 1$. In this case, one has $|x|_p = p^{-\gamma(x)}$ (see [3]).

Let $a \in \mathbb{Q}_p$ and $r > 0$. The set

$$\overline{B}(a, r) := \{x \in \mathbb{Q}_p : |x - a| \leq r\}$$

is called the *closed ball with radius r about a* . (Indeed, $B(a, r)$ is closed in the induced topology). Similarly,

$$B(a, r) := \{x \in \mathbb{Q}_p : |x - a| < r\}$$

is called the *open ball with radius r about a* . It is easy to see that every ball in ultrametric spaces is a closed and open set. We use the word ‘‘clopen’’ as an abbreviation of ‘‘closed and open’’.

We recall that $\mathbb{Z}_p = \{x \in \mathbb{Q}_p : |x|_p \leq 1\}$ and $\mathbb{Z}_p^* = \{x \in \mathbb{Q}_p : |x|_p = 1\}$ are the set of all *p-adic integers* and *p-adic units*, respectively.

Consider a dynamical system (f, X) in \mathbb{Q}_p , where $f : x \in X \mapsto f(x) \in X$ is an analytic function and $X = B(a, r)$ or \mathbb{Q}_p . Denote $x^{(n)} = f^n(x^{(0)})$, where $x^{(0)} \in X$ and $f^n(x) = \underbrace{f \circ \dots \circ f}_n(x)$. If $f(x^{(0)}) = x^{(0)}$ then $x^{(0)}$ is called a *fixed point*. A fixed point $x^{(0)}$ is called an

attractor if there exists a neighborhood $U(x^{(0)}) (\subset X)$ of $x^{(0)}$ such that for all points $y \in U(x^{(0)})$ it holds $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} y^{(n)} = x^{(0)}$, where $y^{(n)} = f^n(y)$. If $x^{(0)}$ is an attractor then its *basin of attraction* is

$$A(x^{(0)}) = \{y \in \mathbb{Q}_p : y^{(n)} \rightarrow x^{(0)}, n \rightarrow \infty\}.$$

A fixed point $x^{(0)}$ is called *repeller* if there exists a neighborhood $U(x^{(0)})$ of $x^{(0)}$ such that $|f(x) - x^{(0)}|_p > |x - x^{(0)}|_p$ for $x \in U(x^{(0)})$, $x \neq x^{(0)}$. For a fixed point $x^{(0)}$ of a function $f(x)$ a ball $B(x^{(0)}, r)$ (contained in X) is said to be a *Siegel disc* if each sphere $S(x^{(0)}, \rho)$, $\rho < r$ is an invariant sphere of $f(x)$, i.e. if $x \in S(x^{(0)}, \rho)$ then all iterated points $x^{(n)} \in S(x^{(0)}, \rho)$ for all $n = 1, 2, \dots$. The union of all Siegel discs with the center at $x^{(0)}$ is said to be a *maximum Siegel disc* and is denoted by $SI(x^{(0)})$.

Let $x^{(0)}$ be a fixed point of an analytic function $f(x)$. Set

$$\lambda = \frac{d}{dx} f(x^{(0)}).$$

The point $x^{(0)}$ is called *attractive* if $0 \leq |\lambda|_p < 1$, *indifferent* if $|\lambda|_p = 1$, and *repelling* if $|\lambda|_p > 1$.

We explore the basic properties of the 2-adic Ising mapping which is given by

$$f_a(x) = \left(\frac{ax + 1}{x + a} \right)^2$$

where $a \in \mathbb{Q}_2 \setminus \{-1, 0, 1\}$.

By $\mathcal{R}(f_a)$ we denote a set of all ‘‘bad points’’ of the Ising mapping, i.e.

$$\mathcal{R}(f_a) = \{x \in \mathbb{Q}_2 : \exists n \geq 0 \text{ such that } f_a^n(x) = a\}.$$

It is easy to see that a domain of the 2-adic Ising mapping is the following set

$$\text{Dom}(f_a) = \mathbb{Q}_2 \setminus \mathcal{R}(f_a).$$

In [2] dynamics of the p -adic Ising mapping was studied for $p \geq 3$. In this work we investigate the dynamics of the Ising mapping over \mathbb{Q}_2 .

For a given $x \in \mathbb{Q}_2$ we define a positive orbit or trajectory of the point under the Ising mapping as follows $\{f_a^n(x) : n \in \mathbb{Z}_+\}$. Let $x \in \mathbb{Q}_2 \setminus \mathcal{R}(f_a)$. Then by $\omega_{f_a}(x)$ we denote a set of all limit points of the positive trajectory.

Now we investigate the set $\omega_{f_a}(x)$. Let us denote

$$x_{\pm} = \frac{(a-1)^2 - 2 \pm (a-1)\sqrt{(a-3)(a+1)}}{2}. \tag{1}$$

One can see that $x_{\pm} \in \mathbb{Q}_2$ if and only if $\sqrt{(a-3)(a+1)}$ exists in \mathbb{Q}_2 .

Theorem 1. Let $a \in \mathbb{Q}_2 \setminus \mathbb{Z}_2$ and f_a be the 2-adic Ising mapping. Then for any $x \in \text{Dom}(f_a)$ it holds

$$\omega_{f_a}(x) = \begin{cases} x_-, & \text{if } x \in 2\mathbb{Z}_2, \\ 1, & \text{if } x \in \mathbb{Z}_2^*, \\ x_+, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Here x_- and x_+ are given by (1).

Theorem 2. Let $a \in (1 + 4\mathbb{Z}_2)$ and f_a be the 2-adic Ising mapping. Then for arbitrary $x \in \text{Dom}(f_a)$ it holds $\omega_{f_a}(x) = \{1\}$.

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